

Innovative Uses of Alternate Refrigeration Systems

D. Boyadzhiev¹, and H. Lam²

¹Msc Electrical Engineering, Aalto University

²Bsc Mechanical Engineering, Aalto University

We live in an era of speed – fast internet, fast food, fast cooling and fast heating. And in this desire for speed in some processes we often forget that each step is contributing to polluting the Earth. Looking especially at the problem of cooling, we stumbled upon a fridge made of clay which does not need any electricity but is instead powered by moisture. We have analyzed the areas or sectors in both the developing and developed nations where it could fit in and has the possibility of being a super energy saver by taking the place of an intermediate cooler. Some innovations in the design, engineering, the marketing, the product placement and existing systems have been suggested to make the product a success and overcome its perceived and inherent weaknesses.